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Legal Framework for the Development of Social Competence in Preschool Children

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Abstract: *This article presents the regulatory framework for the formation of social competence in preschool children in Uzbekistan, as well as the main components of social competence, methods for the formation of social competence and practical recommendations on this issue.*

Key words: *legal framework, social competence, preschool children, main competence, realizing.*

Introduction. The modern world, characterized by rapid changes and globalization, requires from a person not only intellectual abilities, but also developed social competence. Social competence is a set of knowledge, abilities, skills and qualities that allow a person to successfully interact with others, build productive relationships, resolve conflicts, adapt to changing conditions and live in harmony with society.

The formation of social competence in children is the basis for their harmonious development and successful socialization. Realizing the importance of this process, Uzbekistan attaches great importance to the education of socially competent citizens and includes the formation of social skills in the basis of educational policy.

Uzbekistan has a solid legal framework that regulates and ensures the process of forming social competence in children in the preschool and school education system.

Table 1. Main legal acts.

Regulatory documents	Basic Provisions
Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2023)	Guarantees the right to education, freedom of thought and speech, and the right to freely express one's own views (Article 50).
Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education" (2020)	Defines the goals of education, including the formation of a harmoniously developed personality capable of independent life in society (Article 5).
State educational standards for preschool education (2020)	They define the requirements for the content and organization of the educational process in preschool educational institutions, including the development of social competencies in children.
Model Regulations on Preschool Educational Institutions (2020)	Establishes requirements for educational programs, methodological materials and staffing of preschool educational institutions, including on issues of children's social development.
National Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2017-2021 (2017)	Notes the importance of developing human capital and forming social competencies in children as the basis for the successful development of the country
Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2017)	Sets the goal of improving the quality of education and developing social responsibility among young people
Concept of development of preschool education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan (2019)	Emphasizes the importance of developing social skills in children at an early age as a basis for their harmonious development

Active interaction with parents is key to achieving the goals of developing social skills in children. In this area, parent meetings, consultations, seminars, and master classes are held, where parents can receive information about the importance of social competence and methods for developing it in children.

Table 2. Main components of social competence.

Component	Description
Social communication	The ability to interact with other people, build productive relationships, express your thoughts and feelings, listen and understand others.
Social responsibility	Understanding your rights and responsibilities, respect for the rules and laws of society, willingness to help others and take responsibility for your actions.
Emotional regulation	The ability to manage your emotions, control your actions, and react to situations calmly and adequately.
Social thinking	The ability to see a situation from another person's point of view, take into account his interests, and understand the motives of his behavior

Cooperation	Ability to work in a team, solve problems together, share responsibility, and respect the opinions of others.
Tolerance and respect for differences	The ability to accept people with different views, cultures, religions, and respect for the diversity of the world.

In Uzbekistan, work is underway to create specialized centers for additional education that provide an opportunity to develop social skills in children. These centers conduct various trainings, games, classes that help children develop communication skills, work in a team, resolve conflicts, show creativity, etc.

The use of information and communication technologies opens up new opportunities for the formation of social competence in children and helps in a more effective organization of the educational process. For example, teachers can use online platforms to organize distance learning, to provide access to additional materials and games, to conduct online trainings and consultations for parents.

One of the important tasks is the development and implementation of effective methodological materials in the educational process that contribute to the formation of social competence. In this direction, work is underway to create teaching aids, didactic games, board games, simulators and other materials that help children develop social skills in the learning process. In Uzbekistan, active work is underway to create innovative educational programs aimed at developing social competencies in children. For example, some preschool educational institutions have implemented the program “Development of social competence in preschoolers,” which is based on game methods, project activities, and interactive forms of learning.

Table 3. Methods of developing social competence.

Method	Description	Examples
Game methods	Games are a natural form of learning for children, allowing them to learn new things and skills while having fun.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role-playing games: “Family”, “Shop”, “Post Office”, etc.; • educational games: “Collect the picture”, “Find the pair”, “What’s extra?”, etc.; • outdoor games: “Catch the ball”, “Catch-up”, “Hide and Seek”, etc.;
Project activities	Projects allow children to solve creative problems in a team, learn to interact, share responsibility and come to a common decision.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Our Home” - children design and create a model of their home, learn to work in a team, distribute tasks and share responsibility; • “Green City” - children study environmental issues and develop projects for greening their yard or neighborhood.
Modeling social situations	The use of role-playing games and situational tasks allows children to practice different	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “In the store” - children learn how to properly address a salesperson, pay for goods, and

	behavior options in social situations.	choose products; • “Visiting” - children learn the rules of politeness and behavior when visiting.
Conversations and discussions	Conversations on moral and ethical topics help develop children’s critical thinking, ability to analyze situations and make moral choices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion of fairy tales and stories with a moral underlying text; • conversations about friendship, respect, kindness; • discussion of problems in society.
Creative activities	Drawing, modeling, music and theatre allow children to express their emotions, feelings, thoughts and improve interaction with others.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drawing pictures on the themes of friendship, mercy, peace; • dramatization of fairy tales and stories with a moral subtext: • creation of musical compositions on the themes of love, kindness, peace.
Reading fiction	Books are an inexhaustible source of moral and ethical values that contribute to the development of social competence in children.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reading fairy tales, stories, novellas, poems with a moral subtext; • discussion of the works read.

Conclusion. In Uzbekistan, active work is being carried out to develop social competence in children. The regulatory framework provides ample opportunities for the implementation of these tasks, and the practical implementation of innovative methods and technologies contributes to more effective development of social skills in children. Social competence is formed not only at school, but also in the family and in society. Therefore, it is necessary to create a unified system of education that would contribute to the harmonious development of the child's personality and his preparation for a successful life in the modern world.

Practical recommendations:

1. Implementation of innovative educational programs: Development and implementation of modern educational programs and methodological materials aimed at developing social competence in children. The programs should take into account the age characteristics of children and the specifics of developing social skills in different age groups.
2. Improving the qualifications of teachers: Conducting special trainings and advanced training courses for teachers aimed at mastering the methods and technologies of developing social competence. Teachers should gain knowledge about social competence, its components, methods and technologies of its development, as well as the practical application of this knowledge in working with children.
3. Active interaction with parents: Organizing parent-teacher meetings, consultations, joint events to develop social skills in children. Parents should be informed about the importance of social

competence for children and participate in the process of its development, creating a favorable atmosphere in the family and supporting positive social skills in the child.

4. Creation of special centers for the development of social competence: Opening additional education centers for children, where they can develop social skills in a playful and creative way. Such centers should provide opportunities for developing communication skills, teamwork, conflict resolution, creative expression, etc.

Use of information and communication technologies: Use of online platforms and mobile applications to provide parents with information on the formation of social competence and to organize joint activities. Modern technologies can help in the implementation of innovative educational programs, providing access to additional materials, organizing online training for teachers and parents.

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